

O‘TLOQLASHIB BORAYOTGAN TAQIRSIMON TUPROQLAR SHAROITIDA SOYA NAVLARINING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Qashqadaryo viloyatining o‘tloqlashib borayotgan taqirsimon tuproqlari sharoitida kuzgi bug‘doydan so‘ng takroriy ekin sifatida soya o‘simligini yetishtirishda o‘simlikning sug‘orish tartiblariga mos ravishda rivojlanish dinamikasi bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Soya, o‘shish, rivojlanish, takroriy ekin, sug‘orish tartiblari, hosildorlik.

ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the dynamics of development in accordance with the irrigation procedures of the plant when growing a soybean plant as a repeated crop after autumn wheat in the conditions of the grazing takyr soils of the Kashkadarya region.

Key words: Soybeans, growth, development, repeated cultivation, irrigation procedures, productivity.

KIRISH: Dunyo aholisining ko‘payishi oziq-ovqat jumladan, o‘simlik moyi va oqsilli mahsulotlarga bo‘lgan talab kun sayin ortib bormoqda. O‘simlik moyi ishlab chiqarish sanoatida soya va kungaboqar asosiy xomashyo manbai bo‘lib hisoblanadi. «Bugungi kunda yer yuzida 122,1 mln. gektar maydonda soya va 25,6 mln. gektar maydonda kungaboqar asosiy va takroriy muddatlarda yetishtirilmoqda. Dunyo mamlakatlarida bugungi kunda agrar sohada ekinlarni yetishtirishda suv tanqisligi muammosi kundan kunga ortib bormoqda. Moyli ekinlar yetishtiruvchi mamlakatlarda

hosildorlikni oshirish, sifatini yaxshilashda sug'orish muddatlari va me'yorlarini to'g'ri belgilash muhim hisoblanadi.

Qashqadaryo viloyatining o'tloqlashib borayotgan taqirsimon tuproqlari sharoitida takroriy ekin sifatida moyli ekinlardan soya va kungaboqar navlarining maqbul sug'orish tartibini ishlab chiqish hamda bu borada dala va ishlab chiqarish tajribalari o'tkazish, ilmiy asoslangan xulosalar berish agrar soxasidagi muhim masala hisoblanadi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI.

Qashqadaryo viloyatining o'tloqlashib borayotgan taqirsimon tuproqlari sharoitida kuzgi bug'doydan so'ng ekilgan soya o'simliklariga qo'llanilgan agrotadbirlar o'simliklarning o'sishi va rivojlanishiga ham o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatganligi ma'lum bo'ldi.

Dala tajribasini olib borish dasturida ko'rsatilgandek, har xil sug'orish tartibida takroriy ekin soyaning rivojlanish davomiyligi kuzatilganda, ekilgandan maysalashgacha bo'lgan davr mobaynida variantlar o'rtasida deyarli katta farq kuzatilmaganligi qayd etildi.. Ammo, maysalagandan gullashgacha, gullashdan dukkakashgacha, dukkakashdan pishishgacha bo'lgan davrlarda rivojlanish davomiyligi eng ko'p bo'lgan kunlar tegishli 10, 24, 26, 41 kun tajribaning 1-variantida, eng qisqa kunlar tajribaning 2-variantida sug'orishlar tuproqning 0–50 sm hisobiy qatlami bo'yicha cheklangan dala nam sig'imiga ko'ra 65–65–60 % namlik bo'yicha o'tkazilganda, yuqoridagiga muvofiq holda 12,20, 22, 31 kunga to'g'ri keldi. Soyanning vegetatsiya davrining davomiyligi o'rganilganda, eng qisqa muddatda pishib yetilishi ham qayd qilingan tajribaning 2-variantida 83-kun, eng ko'p muddat xo'jalik sharoitida qabul qilingan ishlab chiqarish usuli bo'yicha sug'orilgan 1-variantida 101 kun bo'ldi. Tajribaning 3, 4, va 5 variantlari oraliq o'rinni egalladi.

1-jadval

Soya navlarining rivojlanish dinamikasi, kun 2018 yil

Var.	Navlar	Tuproq nam- ligi ChDNS ga nisb, %	Ko'chat soni, ming tup/ga	Ekilgan- dan maysa- lashgacha	Maysa- lagash gullash- gacha	Gullash- dan dukkak- lashgacha	Dukkak- dan pi- shish- gacha	Amal davri, kun
1	Orzu	70-70-60	212,7	12	20	25	41	98
2	Arleta	65-65-60	214,9	11	16	21	34	82
3		75-75-65	214,8	12	17	23	37	89
4		65-65-60	215,5	11	16	23	36	86
5		75-75-65	215,1	12	18	25	38	93

Poyaning balandligi tahlil qilinganda, bosh poyaning eng yuqori balandligi 4 ta chin barg chiqarganda, 1-dukkak hosil bo'lgungacha, gullash-pishish va o'rim oldidan tajribaning sug'orish suvlari ChDNS ga nisbatan 75–75–65 % namlikda, hisobiy tuproq qatlami 70 sm.gacha bo'lgan sharoitda tajribaning 5-variantida namoyon bo'ldi, tegishli 16,4; 34,1; 80,3 va 86,3 sm.ga teng bo'ldi. O'simlik bo'yining eng past ko'rsatkichi tajribaning ishlab chiqarish sharoitidagi 1-variantida kuzatildi va tegishli 14,2; 26,9; 64,7; 69,6 santimetrni tashkil qildi. Tajribaning 2, 3, 4-variantlaridagi o'sish va rivojlanish holatlari oraliq o'rinni egalladi. O'simliklarda hosil shoxlarining paydo bo'lishi kuzatilganda, sug'orishning har xil me'yorda va muddatda olib borilishi hosil shoxlari soniga hamda bug'in oraliqlariga o'ziga xos ravishda o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatdi. Kam sondagi hosil shoxlari sug'orishlar ishlab chiqarish usulida olib borilgan tajribaning 1-variantida kuzatildi va o'rim oldidan 1,6 donani tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, eng yuqori sondagi hosil shoxlari sug'orish suvlari tuproqning 0–70 sm qatlamidagi namlik darajasi ChDNS ga nisbatan 75–75–65 % sug'orish oldi tuproq namligi bo'yicha sug'orilgan 5-variantda kuzatildi va o'rim oldidan 2,3 donani tashkil qildi. Boshqa variantlardagi hosil shoxlari soni oraliq o'rinni egalladi (2-jadvalda keltirilgan).

2-jadval

Soya navlarining poya balandligi, sm 2018 yil

Variantlar.	Navlar	Sug'.oldi tuproq namligi ChDNS ga nisb, %	Qat- lam, sm	Poya balandligi, sm			
				4 ta chin barg	Gullash	1-duk- kak- gacha,	Pishish davrida, poya balandligi, sm.
1	Orzu	70-70-60	-	14,4	24,6	67,7	69,9
2	Arleta	65-65-60	0-50	13,7	26,1	70,4	74,4
3		75-75-65	0-50	16,7	29,3	77,6	83,8
4		65-65-60	0-70	15,9	27,4	73,8	79,2
5		75-75-65	0-70	17,8	30,9	83,4	88,7

Sug'orish oldi hisobiy qatlamlarning va sug'orish tartiblarining har xil bo'lishi kungaboqar navlari morfologik tuzilishlariga turli xil darajada o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatdi. Nazorat sifatida o'rganilgan, ishlab chiqarish sharoitida sug'orish amalga oshirilgan "Jahongir" navi 1-variant savatchasining diametri 17,7 sm, poyasining diametri 2,2 sm.ni, barglar soni 15,4 donani, barglar uzunligi 15,9 sm va eni 11,8 sm.ni, 1000 dona urug' vazni 97,1 grammni tashkil qildi va bir gektar maydondan olingan hosil 20,9 sentnerga teng bo'ldi.

XULOSA: Yuqori ko'rsatkichlar va kungaboqarda urug' hosili 29,8 s/ga tajribaning 0–70 sm hisobiy qatlam olinib sug'orish ishlari amalga oshirilgan variant va tuproq namligi ChDNS ga nisbatan 65–65–60 % chegarasida sug'orishlar olib borilgan variantda kuzatildi.

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